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QR-Article

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EXTENDED FRAUD TRIANGLE MODEL: MODERATING EFFECT OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AND RISK MANAGEMENT

Abstract: *This research used a broaden fraud triangle model by adding two new variables as a moderator which are good corporate governance and company risk management. The samples in this research are direction board of directors and public insurance company commissioners in Indonesia. The application of GCG is measured by GCG index by using worksheet that is published by regulator, whilst implementation of risk management is measured by using risk management index. The hypothesis in this research is examined by using structural equation model to fraud triangle model and Moderated Regression Analysis to influence the moderation from GCG and risk management. Characteristics of a company such as size, insurance sector, as well as board of direction composition and commissioners as another variable which is evaluated its influence partially towards the variable or the relationship between research variables.*

Keywords: *Fraud, Fraud Triangle Model, Theory of Planned Behavior, GCG, risk management.*

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РАСШИРЕННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ ТРЕУГОЛЬНИКА МОШЕННИЧЕСТВА: СМЯГЧАЮЩИЙ ЭФФЕКТ КОРПОРАТИВНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ И УПРАВЛЕНИЯ РИСКАМИ

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Аннотация: В этом исследовании использовалась расширенная модель треугольника мошенничества путем добавления двух новых переменных в качестве модератора, которые являются хорошим корпоративным управлением и управлением рисками компании. Образцами в этом исследовании являются совет директоров дирекции и уполномоченные государственных страховых компаний в Индонезии. Применение GCG измеряется индексом GCG с использованием рабочего листа, опубликованного регулирующим органом, в то время как внедрение управления рисками измеряется с помощью индекса управления рисками. Гипотеза в этом исследовании проверяется с помощью модели структурных уравнений для модели треугольника мошенничества и регрессионного анализа с модерированием, чтобы повлиять на модерирование со стороны GCG и управления рисками. Характеристики компании, такие как размер, сектор страхования, а также состав совета директоров и уполномоченных в качестве еще одной переменной, которая частично оценивает ее влияние на переменную или взаимосвязь между переменными исследования.

Ключевые слова: Мошенничество, Модель треугольника мошенничества, Теория запланированного поведения, GCG, управление рисками.

Introduction

Fraud problem becomes a center of attention when there is a global financial crisis which starts in 2007. [Stanton, 2011] states that company management fails to protect the ownership and as a stakeholder in company. That failure makes the company realize of the importance of good corporate governance to anticipate and predict similar events in the future. Insurance corporate governance has an important role to convince and gain trust from the stakeholders, especially consumers and investors, that insurance company has been managed based on transparency, fairness, accountability, responsibility, and independency.

[Richins, 2014] states that fraud is one of the main failure causes which decreases the company image, especially in the last ten years. There are some special ways which can be done by the company to decrease and omit that fraud. Hiring internal or external auditors, creating cultural etiquette, implementation of computer programs, using whistleblower, management surveillance in micro level, fixing package for employee's compensation, as well as giving out sanctions or punishments towards any kinds of fraud. According to Lin et al, fraud in a company creates a financial hindrance in the means of a company that experience fraud shows sensitivity towards a positive cash flow after the fraud occurs. The result of this research shows that fraud may have a concrete impact towards the company performance through the impact on external financial expenses and internal cash authority. Fraud in financial report is still a huge problem although there is a legislative effort and study from [Odom and Ugrin, 2014] which helps in identifying how to rationalize a

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fraud, when the consequences can be anticipated, as well as why the prevention is ineffective.

[Haithem et al., 2014] states that the cause of fraud is not universal and its impact towards the involvement of fraud is probably influenced by cultural factor in a wide range of levels, society level which leads to individualism dimension or collectivism, as well as idiocentrism/allocentrism which is cultural conceptualism level as individual. Thus, the understanding towards a wide range of cultures in the fraud will enrich knowledge about how and why the fraud may occur, how the fraud can be detected, and how the fraud can be controlled. According to [Cumming et al., 2011], current research about the fraud indicating factors in the companies in developing countries, mainly is focused on the mechanism of internal governance and a small part of them is about the impact of the presence of external party, such as involving an analyst. [Biljanoska, 2015] mentioned that implementation of risk management system in general is the base of detecting and preventing fraud.

[KNKG, 2009] states that insurance company is a company which promises protection towards the consumers and or people who have the polis as well as gathering people funding. Both of these roles experience a rapid growth which therefore requires insurance company that is strong and reliable. Insurance industry which consists of insurance company, reinsurance company, and supporting insurance company which operate in sharia system, must uphold insurance principles especially utmost good faith principle and good corporate governance implementation to fulfill the responsibility as promised. GCG must be understood as well by the stakeholders hence the insurance industry can develop better.

The implementation of risk management effectively has an aim to ensure that the risk can be understood, managed, and if necessary, can be communicated to the stakeholders. The implementation of risk management is getting more popular in many kinds of economy sector, especially in financial institution which is a trigger as well as the most severe part that receives major impact of global financial crisis. [OECD, 2014] states that a huge surprise from the global financial crisis is the failure in implementing risk management in a company. One of the consequences which have a massive impact is financial fraud which occurs in the companies, even in the top-level management. This matter is strongly related with business etiquette problem and also breaks the trust of stakeholders. This fraud is even affecting the bankruptcy of companies and lawsuits in several corporate which operate in international level.

Two main factors which are considered to decrease the fraud risk in insurance industry are the implementation of good corporate governance and risk management of insurance companies. However, in this condition, the implementation of GCG and risk management in Indonesian insurance industry is relatively new if it is seen from

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the OJK new regulations which have been published only in the last two years, which are in 2014 and 2015. This condition shows that GCG implementation and risk management relatively are not yet implemented entirely and in general in insurance industry. Hence, it is predicted to have an impact on identification attempt and fraud risk management.

Identification of fraud risk and its management can be seen from the perspectives of board of directors and commissioners from public insurance company in Indonesia. Implementation of GCG in insurance industry in Indonesia relies on the regulation of GCG which is released by Otoritas Jasa Keuangan (OJK). Implementation of risk management in insurance companies also relies on the regulation of OJK as well as the issued letter about the risk of insurance company evaluation. The risk evaluation process is measured by perception from board of directors and commissioners, including the evaluation towards the fraud risk which is experienced or encountered in the company.

The aim of this research is to obtain information or a valid data which is reliable and based on the facts also empirical data that can be explained as: (1) To know and analyze if the principles of corporate governance is good, which consists of accountability, transparency, responsibility, independency, and fairness, influencing towards the fraud in insurance industry, and (2) to know and analyze if the implementation risk management process, which consists of risk identification, risk analysis, evaluation, and risk management influence a decrease in number of frauds in insurance industry.

Literature Review

Fraud Triangle Model

According to The Institute of Internal [of Internal Auditor, 2009], the understanding of fraud is:

Any illegal act characterized by deceit, concealment, or violation of trust. These acts are not dependent upon the threat of violence or physical force. Frauds are perpetrated by parties and organizations to obtain money, property, or services; to avoid payment or loss of services; or to secure personal or business advantage

In the insurance context, National Association of Insurance Commissioners (NAIC) states that insurance fraud happens when the insurance company, agent, and loss evaluation, as well as consumers do fraud intentionally to gain an advantage which is illegal.

Fraud Triangle Model is first stated by Donald R. Cresses in 1973 and becomes one of the research models that is used as a reference and continues to develop until present time. [Mackevicius and Giriunas, 2013] explain that the model transformation seems like this figure below.

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According to [of Internal Auditor, 2009], fraud risk evaluation generally consists of three main steps which are: (1) Fraud risk factors identification which are relevant, (2) Potential fraud scheme identification and creating its priority based on its risk level, (3) Surveillance mapping that exists in order to find the potential fraud scheme and to identify the inequality, (4) examining the effectiveness of operational fraud prevention and detection surveillance, and (5) documentation and report of fraud risk evaluation. Prevention process and fraud risk detection can be seen in the figure below:

Research done by [Aghghaleh et al., 2014] used the fraud triangle model from financial and management perspective which analyzes the relationship between companies experience in fraud with factors such as sales to credit ratio, debts to assets ratio, the total number of auditing committee, and total number of board of directors. Some researchers that use that model is [Boulter et al., 2013] who use the statistic approach, which is the regression analysis, to know the financial factors and management structural which affect the experience of the company's fraud occurrence in Malaysia.

Figure 1: Fraud Triangle Model Evolution [Mackevicius and Giriuнас, 2013]

Figure 2: Prevention, detection, and fraud investigation [of Internal Auditor, 2009].

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Good Corporate Governance

According to [Kostyuk et al., 2007], the term of “Corporate Governance” can be interpreted as narrow and broad which are connected with two perspectives, which are shareholders and stakeholders. In the narrow perspective, governance is a relationship between company managers, board of directors, and shareholders. While in broad perspectives, governance includes combination of laws, regulations, share issuance regulation, and practices in managing private companies in which the company attracts capital, operates efficiently, and generates profits, as well as fulfilling responsibility and people’s expectation.

[Claessens, 2003] states that the understanding governance can be classified into two groups. First group emphasizes on the behavior patterns which are actual behavior of companies in different measurements, such as performance, efficiency, growth, financial structure, and treatment to the shareholders and stakeholders. The second group emphasizes on the normative working framework which are regulations whereas a company that operates are from law system, judicial system, financial markets, and labor market.

Referring to World Bank, the governance of a company consists of four pillars which are accountability, fairness, transparency, and responsibility. Accountability assures that management ranks are responsible to the board of directors, and board of directors is responsible to the shareholders. Fairness pillar protects the rights of shareholders, treating every shareholder in fairness and justice, including the minority of shareholders. Transparency pillar assures the rate and accuracy of revealing important information, including financial situation, performance, ownership, and governance. The last pillar is responsibility which understands the rights of shareholders and encourages cooperation between companies and stakeholders in order to create welfare, employment, and economy sustainability.

The governance principles according to OECD briefly includes:

- (1) Ensure that basic working framework of governance is effective;
- (2) Rights of shareholders and functions of controlling shareholders;
- (3) Fair treatment towards the shareholders;
- (4) The role of shareholders in corporate governance;
- (5) Revealing and transparency;
- (6) Directors responsibility.

In OECD 2004, it is stated that: “working framework of company governance must encourage transparency and efficient market, along with the laws and regulations, and divides clearly the responsibility and obligation between the authorities which conduct surveillance function, regulations, and law enforcement.”

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Figure 3: Conceptual framework by [Haithem et al., 2014]

OJK regulation explicitly regulates risk management or risk management implementation which is in Peraturan Otoritas Jasa Keuangan Nomor 2/POJK.05/2014 about good corporate governance for insurance companies. A good corporate governance is a structure and process that is used and implemented in insurance industry to increase target of profit and to optimize the value of a company for all the stakeholders

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especially the polis holders, participants and or other parties that gain benefit, in terms of accountable and in regards to the values in law as well as etiquette values.

Risk Management

The understanding of risk management in terms of editorial differs from one institution to another, even though in terms of substantive, it is relatively similar. Some understandings of risk management from international institution are as follows:

1. General management functions which identify, evaluate, and manage the cause and effect from uncertainty and risk from organization. (LOMA)
2. Identification, analysis, and risk management which may threaten operation, asset, and other responsibilities from an organization. (CII)
3. Risk management of a company is a process, which is influenced by board of directors, management, and other personals, implemented in strategy implementation as well as to include entire company, designed to identify potential events that may affect business entity, as well as to manage risks as in the estimated risk which is expected by the company to provide proper assurance with the reach of company goal. (COSO)
4. Systematic process through understanding, evaluation, and risk management to maximize the opportunity to reach the goal and assure the organization, individual, and people. (IRM)
5. The coordinated events to direct and control organization as in line with the risk. (ISO 31000)
6. Process whereas an organization in every industry evaluates, controls, exploits, uses, funds, or surveys the risk from all the resources with the aim of increasing short-term value and long-term value from organization from stakeholders. (CAS)

The understanding of risk management for an insurance company in Indonesia refers to OJK (2014) which is:

The series of procedures and methodology which are used to identify, measure, survey, control the risk may appear from the event in non-bank financial services institutions.

In the year of 2010, three associations - AIRMIC, ALARM, and IRM - together do a completion of company risk management steps which has been arranged in 2002 and is adjusted as standard of ISO 31000. The steps of risk management that have been adjusted with the standard of ISO can be seen as follows:

[Ciorciari and P, 2008] states that the conduction of company risk management framework (ERM/Enterprise Risk Management) encourages and increases the awareness of risk in every management level in a company, from strategic to operational level, and from top management to the employees. Referring to [COSO, 2004]. ERM is a process of risk management of a company, which is influenced by

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board of directors, management, and other personals, implemented in strategy implementation as well as to include entire company, designed to identify potential events that may affect business entity, as well as to manage risks as in the estimated risk which is expected by the company to provide proper assurance with the reach of company goal.

Figure 4: A Structured approach to Enterprise Risk Management [AIRMIC, 2010]

Proposed Research Model

The method that is used in this research is survey method and data collection which aims to know and determine the temporary position of the variables - the evaluated variables are based on the data during the research and connecting between variables that are evaluated. The data sources are from all the board of directors and commissioners in public insurance companies in Indonesia which is by filling in a questionnaire and GCG index and risk management index by top leaders in public insurance company.

The implementation of good corporate governance uses the GCG index that is issued by regulators in Indonesia. The risk management is measured by index that is developed by Monde and Girogino by using several questions that are classified into three fields which are: (1) Risk Cultural, (2) organization, and (3) process. Risk management index measurement uses 22 closed questions which therefore the score will be 0 as the lowest and 100 as the highest. This research model will rely on the fraud triangle model which is developed by [Harrison, 2014]. Fraud triangle model is added with GCG variable. Risk management in insurance companies and public insurance company's characteristics as moderator. The suggested research method can be seen below:

Figure 5: Proposed Research Model

Statistic technique that is used in the model examination or research hypothesis is Structural Equation Model and Moderated Regression Analysis.

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